

Outcome of Spirometric Study in Children with Sickle Cell Disease

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Abstract

Background: Sickle cell disease (SCD) is an autosomal recessive inherited hemoglobinopathy that includes sickle cell anemia and compound heterozygous states where one β -globin allele carries the sickle mutation and the other carries variants such as HbC, β -thalassemia, HbD, or HbOArab. Pulmonary complications are a major cause of morbidity and mortality in SCD, presenting mainly as acute chest syndrome and chronic sickle cell lung disease. Abnormal pulmonary function tests are frequently reported in patients with SCD, even during steady-state conditions. **Aim:** To evaluate the prevalence and patterns of lung function abnormalities using spirometric parameters in patients with SCD attending the Karbala Hereditary Blood Disease Center, compared with healthy non-SCD controls. **Methods:** This case-control cross-sectional study included 40 patients with SCD in steady state and 40 age-matched healthy controls. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire covering demographic characteristics, anthropometric measures, history of vaso-occlusive crises, hospital admissions, and blood transfusions. All participants underwent spirometry, while complete blood count and hemoglobin fractions were assessed in the SCD group only. **Results:** Weight, body mass index, forced vital capacity (FVC% predicted), forced expiratory volume in one second (FEV₁% predicted), and peak expiratory flow (PEF% predicted) were significantly lower in patients with SCD compared with controls ($P < 0.005$). Among SCD patients, age, height, weight, and white blood cell count showed significant negative correlations with FEV₂₅₋₇₅%, PEF%, and FEV₁/FVC. No significant correlations were observed with the type or number of crises. HbS levels correlated negatively with FEV₁/FVC and FEV₂₅₋₇₅%, while HbF levels correlated positively with FVC% predicted. Restrictive lung disease was the most common abnormality (22%), followed by obstructive defects (12%). **Conclusion:** Lung function parameters are significantly reduced in patients with Hb-SS compared with non-SCD controls. Restrictive ventilatory defects are prevalent and are significantly associated with markers of disease severity, particularly white blood cell count and HbS level.

Introduction

Anemia is defined as a reduction in hemoglobin concentration or red blood cell (RBC) mass below the normal range for healthy individuals, with normal values varying according to age and sex [1]. From a morphological perspective, anemia is commonly

classified based on RBC size and hemoglobin content, using parameters derived from the complete blood count, reticulocyte count, and peripheral blood smear, which together guide etiological diagnosis [2]. Sickle cell disease (SCD) is a hereditary hemoglobinopathy transmitted in an autosomal recessive pattern. It

More Information

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results from a point mutation in the β -globin gene, where adenine is replaced by thymine at codon 6, leading to substitution of valine for glutamic acid and production of hemoglobin S (HbS) [3]. SCD encompasses not only homozygous sickle cell anemia (HbSS) but also compound heterozygous states in which HbS is inherited alongside other abnormal β -globin variants such as HbC, β -thalassemia, HbD, or HbOArab. In sickle cell anemia, HbS usually constitutes up to 90% of total hemoglobin, whereas in other sickling disorders it exceeds 50% [1]. Globally, SCD represents the most common inherited genetic disorder affecting populations of African and Caribbean origin, with more than 200 million carriers worldwide and approximately 250,000 affected births annually [4]. In Iraq, SCD shows a distinct geographical clustering, with higher prevalence reported in the southern Arab population and the northern Kurdish regions [5]. The persistence of the HbS gene in malaria-endemic areas is attributed to the protective advantage conferred by sickle cell trait against severe *Plasmodium falciparum* infection [6]. At the molecular level, deoxygenated HbS undergoes polymerization, forming rigid intracellular fibers that distort RBC shape and reduce deformability. These changes predispose erythrocytes to hemolysis and microvascular occlusion, particularly in organs with sluggish blood flow such as the lungs [1,4]. Chronic hemolysis, oxidative stress, endothelial dysfunction, and sterile inflammation further contribute to progressive organ damage, with pulmonary involvement being especially prominent [7,8]. Pulmonary complications are a major cause of morbidity and mortality in SCD and include acute chest syndrome (ACS), chronic sickle cell lung disease, airway hyper-reactivity, sleep-disordered breathing, and pulmonary hypertension [9]. ACS, characterized by fever, respiratory symptoms, and new pulmonary infiltrates, is one of the leading causes of hospitalization and death in SCD, particularly in children [10]. Recurrent ACS episodes and coexisting asthma significantly increase the risk of developing chronic restrictive lung disease later in life [11]. Pulmonary function tests (PFTs), particularly spirometry, are essential tools for assessing respiratory involvement in SCD. Spirometry provides objective measurements of airflow and lung volumes, enabling detection of obstructive, restrictive, or mixed ventilatory defects [12]. In children and adolescents with SCD, spirometry is widely used to monitor lung function, assess disease progression, and identify early pulmonary impairment, even in the absence of overt respiratory symptoms [13]. This study, therefore, aimed to evaluate the prevalence and type of lung function abnormalities using spirometric parameters in SCD patients who attend Karbala hereditary blood disease center.

Method

This analytical cross-sectional study was conducted at Karbala Teaching Hospital for Children, which includes the Karbala Hereditary Blood Disease Center, between May and December 2022. The study population comprised 40 children with sickle cell disease (SCD) and 40 age-matched healthy non-SCD controls. Patients with SCD were recruited during routine follow-up visits or contacted by telephone. Eligible patients were aged ≥ 5 years, in a steady-state condition, and had clearly documented hemoglobin electrophoresis results in their medical records. The control group consisted of healthy children selected from primary schools and relatives of healthcare workers who were not attending hospital services. All referred SCD patients aged more than 5 years were eligible for inclusion. Exclusion criteria included the presence of acute painful crisis, respiratory symptoms, severe anemia requiring blood transfusion, or inability to perform acceptable spirometry maneuvers. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire that captured sociodemographic characteristics and relevant medical history. Anthropometric measurements, including weight, height, and body mass index (BMI), were obtained for all participants. Spirometry was performed for both groups in accordance with the American Thoracic Society/European Respiratory Society (ATS/ERS) guidelines using a WinSpiroPRO 8.2 spirometer. At least three acceptable and reproducible maneuvers were obtained, and the best values for forced vital capacity (FVC) and forced expiratory volume in one second (FEV_1) were recorded. Spirometric parameters (FVC, FEV_1 , FEF_{25-75} , and peak expiratory flow [PEF]) were expressed as percentages of predicted values adjusted for the Oriental population using Knudson reference equations, while the FEV_1/FVC ratio was recorded as the actual measured value. Lower airway obstruction was defined as $FEV_1 < 80\%$ predicted with FVC $> 80\%$ predicted and $FEV_1/FVC < 80\%$. A restrictive pattern was suggested by FVC $< 80\%$ predicted with $FEV_1/FVC > 0.8$. Bronchodilator reversibility was assessed using 2.5 mg salbutamol via nebulization, with a positive response defined as a $\geq 10\%$ improvement in FEV_1 or FVC after 15 minutes. Complete blood count was performed for SCD patients only. Statistical analysis was conducted using SPSS version 21 and GraphPad software. Continuous variables were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation, while categorical variables were presented as frequencies and percentages. Independent t-tests were used to compare spirometric parameters between groups, Pearson correlation to assess relationships between spirometry and laboratory variables, and Fisher's exact test to compare proportions of spirometric patterns.

Results

Forty children with sickle cell disease (SCD) were enrolled in the study and compared with 40 age-matched non-sickled healthy controls. As shown in Table 3.1, the mean age of SCD patients was 11.9 ± 5.0 years, which was comparable to that of the control group (11.0 ± 3.0 years; P = 0.463). Similarly, there was no statistically significant difference in mean height between the two groups (137.0 ± 19.7 cm in SCD patients versus 144.6 ± 19.7 cm in controls; P = 0.11). In contrast, significant differences were observed in

anthropometric measures related to body mass. The mean body weight of SCD participants was significantly lower than that of the control group (34.0 ± 16.9 kg vs 46.0 ± 22.7 kg; P = 0.010). Likewise, body mass index (BMI) was markedly reduced among children with SCD compared with non-SCD controls (16.6 ± 3.0 vs 21.9 ± 11.0 kg/m²; P = 0.007). These findings indicate that, despite comparable age and height, children with SCD had significantly lower weight and BMI than healthy controls. As in table 1.

Table 1: Demographic Character of SCD Patients and Non-SCD Control

Parameters	SCD (n=40)	Non-SCD(n=40)	P value
Age (year)	11.9±5	11±3	0.463
Height (cm)	137±19.7	137±19.7	0.11
Weight (kg)	34±16.9	46±22.7	0.010
BMI	16.6±3	21.9±11	0.007

Note: Data presented by mean±SD *significant p value<0.05

Table 2 and 3 shows that lung function parameters of the SCD participants compared to non-SCD control, the mean FVC and FEV1%predicted of the SCD participants were 86.7 ±16.7 % and 89.4±17% respectively, compared to102.3±13.8% and 104.3±11.3 respectively among the non-SCD control (P=0.007and 0.000), also

showed that PEF among SCD patients was 89±25.6% compared to 108±17.5% among controls(P=0.000). Table 4 FVC and FEV1 were significantly lower among participants in urban than rural area. Table 5 comparing abnormal spirometric result between the SCD and non-SCD control participants there is a significant difference (P=0.003)

Table 2: Spirometric Parameters of SCD Participants and Non-SCD Control

Parameters	SCD (n=40)	Control (n=40)	P value
FVC	86.7±16.7	102.3±13.8	0.007*
FEV1	89.4±17	104.3±11.3	0.00*
FEV1/FVC	0.90	0.90	0.788
PEF	89±25.6	108±17.5	0.00*
FEF 25-57	93±25	103±20.9	0.06
	N	Mean±sd	
WBC	40	8.4±3.3	
Platelet	40	302±144	
Hb	40	9.8±2.8	
HbS	40	66±7.5	
HbF	40	20±9.6	
HbA	27	9.9±7.9	

Note: Data presented by mean±SD *Significant p value<0.05

Table 3: Demographic and Clinical Characteristic of the SCD Patients

Characteristics	Frequency	%	
Sex	Male	21	52
	Female	19	48
Living	Urban	26	65
	Rural	14	35
Family history of allergy	Positive	15	37
	Negative	25	62.5
Passive smoking	Positive	20	50
	Negative	20	50
Type of anemia	Sickle	33	82

	Sickle thalassemia	7	18.4
Hospital admission	Negative	19	50.0
	1/pain	6	15.8
	2/pain	2	5.3
	3/pain	3	7.9
	4/pain	2	5.3
	1/respiratory disease	2	5.3
	2/ respiratory disease	2	5.3
	Frequent respiratory disease and pain	1	2.6
Blood transfusion	1/fever	1	2.6
	Once	9	24.3
	Twice	3	8.1
	Frequent	2	5.4
	Negative	23	62.2

Table 4: Association between Living and Spirometric Parameters of SCD Patients

Parameters	Urban (n=26)	Rural (n=14)	p-value
FVC%	81.7±12.13	96±21	0.019*
FEV1%	84.2±13.5	84.2±13.5	0.004*
FEV1/FVC	90.3± 7.2	92.5± 7.2	-0.883
PEF%	86±25.2	95.8±27	0.138
FEF25-75%	89.3±25.8	102.4±23.13	0.067

Note: Data presented by mean±SD *significant p value <0.05

Table 5: Outcome of Spirometric Findings of the Participants

Spirometric result	SCD (%)	Non-SCD (%)	P-value
Normal	26(65%)	37(92%)	0.005*
Abnormal	14(35%)	3(8%)	
Total	40(100%)	40(100%)	

Note: *Significant p value <0.05

Table 6 regarding the correlation between the spirometric parameters and anthropometric parameters of SCD participants there is negative correlation between the age, weight, height and FEF25-57% predicted, PEF%predicted and FEV1/FVC.

Table 7: There is no correlation between number of crisis and spirometric parameters.

Table 8: correlation between spirometric and laboratory parameters show that FVC% predicted negatively correlated with WBC count and positively correlated with Hb.

Table 6: Pearson Correlation between Demographic and Spirometric Parameters of the SCD Participants

		FVC	FEV1	FEV1/FVC	PEF	FEF25-57
Age (year)	Correlation coefficient	0.067	-0.209	-0.709***	-0.431**	-0.459**
	Sig.(2tailed)	0.686	0.201	0.000	0.006	0.003
Height (cm)	Correlation coefficient	0.007	-0.043	-0.643***	-0.451**	-0.39*
	Sig.(2tailed)	0.968	0.794	0.000	0.000	0.014
Weight (kg)	Correlation coefficient	0.173	-0.043	-0.643***	-0.337*	-0.331*
	Sig.(2tailed)	0.293	0.794	0.000	0.036	0.040
BMI	Correlation coefficient	0.278	0.133	-0.482**	-0.081	-0.187
	Sig.(2tailed)	0.086	0.420	0.002	0.622	0.255

Note: *low correlation; **moderate correlation; ***high correlation

Table 7: Pearson Correlation between Number of Crisis and Spirometric Parameters in SCD Participants

		FVC%	FEV1%	FEV1/FVC	FEF25-57%	PEF%
Number of painful crisis	Correlation coefficient	-0.158	-0.248	-0.221	-0.171	-0.044
	Sig.(2-tailed)	0.337	0.128	0.176	0.297	0.790
	N	40	40	40	40	40

Table 8: Correlation between CBC and Spirometric Parameters for SCD Participants

		FVC%	FEV1%	FEV1/FVC	FEF25-57%	PEF%
Platelet	Pearson correlation	-0.275	-0.106	0.232	0.182	0.018
	Sig.(2-tailed)	0.100	0.532	0.166	0.280	0.917
	N	38	38	38	38	38
WBC	Pearson correlation	-0.376*	-0.281	0.289	-0.095	-0.151
	Sig.(2-tailed)	0.022	0.092	0.082	0.575	0.371
	N	38	38	38	38	38
Hb	Pearson correlation	0.340*	0.253	-0.164	0.100	0.212
	Sig.(2-tailed)	0.040	0.131	0.333	0.556	0.208
	N	38	38	38	38	38

Note: Significant p value <0.05 *low correlation

Table 9: the correlation between HbS level and spirometric parameters in SCD patients found negative correlation between HbS level and FEV1/FVC ratio and FEF 25-57% predicted.

Table 10: Positive correlation between HbF level and FVC% predicted.

Table 11: By comparing spirometric parameters between sickle cell anemia (HbSS) and sickle

thalassemia (Hb Sβ0) showed that mean FEF 25-75% predicted was 89.8±24% in sickle anemia compared to 113±16% in sickle thalassemia patient(P=0.015),the mean of FEV1/FVC among sickled was 0.89±0.07compared to 0.95±0.04 in sicklethalassemia patients (P=0.032).

Table 9: Correlation between Hemoglobin S Level in Sickled Patients and Spirometric Parameters

		FVC%	FEV1%	FEV1/FVC	PEF%	FEF25-57%
HbS	Pearson correlation	-0.136	-0.271	-0.366*	-0.256	-0.358*
	Sig.(2-tailed)	0.414	0.099	0.024	0.121	0.027
	N	40	40	40	40	40

Note: Significant p value <0.05 *low correlation

Table 10: Correlation of HbF and Lung Function Parameters

		FVC%	FEV1%	FEV1/FVC	PEF%	FEF 25-75%
HbF	Pearson correlation	0.327*	0.251	-0.1444	0.252	0.087
	Sig.(2-tailed)	0.045	0.128	0.390	0.127	0.602
	N	40	40	40	40	40

Note: Significant p value <0.05 *low correlation

Table 11: Comparing Spirometric Results between Patients with SCD and Sicklethalassemia

	HbSS (n=33)	Hb Sβ0 (n=7)	P value
FVC%	87±18	83±4	0.310
FEV1%	89±18	91±7.5	0.584
FEV1/FVC	0.89±0.07	0.95±0.04	0.032*
PEF%	87±24.7%	99.6±30.5%	0.380
FEF25-75%	89.8±24.9	113±16	0.015*

Note: *Significant p value <0.05

Discussion

Children with sickle cell disease (SCD) are widely reported to have impaired growth and altered pulmonary function compared with non-SCD peers. In the present study, weight and body mass index (BMI) were significantly lower in SCD patients than in controls, while height did not differ significantly. These findings align with reports by Chinawa et al. and Tassel et al., who demonstrated reduced BMI and other

anthropometric indices among children with SCD [14,15]. In contrast, Oguntoye et al. suggested that growth differences become more pronounced after adolescence [16], which may explain the absence of a significant height difference in our relatively young cohort (mean age 11.9 ± 5 years). The reduced anthropometric measures observed may reflect increased metabolic demands, chronic hypoxaemia, and tissue hypoperfusion associated with SCD, all of

which can impair normal growth and development. Pulmonary function was significantly compromised in SCD participants, with lower mean FEV₁%, FVC%, and PEF% predicted compared with controls. Similar reductions in spirometric parameters have been reported in both pediatric and adult SCD populations [17,18]. These abnormalities were observed despite patients being clinically in a steady state, supporting evidence that subclinical vaso-occlusion and chronic inflammation may impair lung function even in asymptomatic periods [19]. Lower weight and BMI in SCD patients may further contribute, as anthropometric measures are important predictors of lung volumes [20]. Additionally, diminished respiratory muscle strength and restricted chest wall movement reported in SCD may exacerbate reductions in lung volumes [21]. Correlation analysis revealed significant negative associations between age, height, and weight with obstructive indices such as FEV₁/FVC, PEF%, and FEF₂₅₋₇₅%. FEF₂₅₋₇₅%, a sensitive marker of small airway disease, declined with age, supporting the concept that airway involvement in SCD may begin in the small airways [14]. Notably, bronchodilator reversibility was observed in all tested patients, suggesting airway hyper-responsiveness, possibly related to subclinical asthma or non-asthmatic inflammatory mechanisms, as proposed by [20]. Environmental and social factors also appeared relevant, as urban residence and family history of allergy were associated with lower lung function parameters, whereas passive smoking and sex were not. Laboratory correlations demonstrated that higher baseline leukocyte counts were associated with reduced FVC%, consistent with prior studies identifying leukocytosis as a marker of disease severity and a contributor to pulmonary vasculopathy and restrictive lung disease [15,18,22]. Conversely, higher steady-state hemoglobin levels correlated positively with FVC%, supporting the link between chronic hemolysis, endothelial dysfunction, and progressive lung injury [23]. Furthermore, higher HbS levels were associated with worse obstructive indices, while HbF showed a protective association with lung volumes, reinforcing the beneficial pulmonary effects of HbF and the potential role of hydroxyurea therapy [24]. Overall, restrictive lung disease was the predominant abnormality, in agreement with multiple studies [15,18,25], although heterogeneity in pulmonary patterns remains well recognized in SCD.

Conclusion

Patients with SCD had a lower mean weight and BMI than age-matched control. Patients with SCD had a significant decline in lung function compared to non-SCD control and associated mainly with restrictive pattern of pulmonary function abnormality. EFV₁/FVC and FEF 25-75% predicted are the main lung function parameters that decline with age. High WBC and HbS

level associated with more decline in lung function parameters while HbF level can have a protective role on lung volumes.

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